

Revolutionising Responsible Fashion Retail with Metaverse: Exploring Generation Z's Perceptions

Inci Toral Manson,
Department of Marketing, Birmingham Business School, University of Birmingham,
UK

i.n.toral.1@bham.ac.uk

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4656-7139>

Selcen Ozturkcan,
Department of Marketing, School of Business and Economics, Linnaeus University,
Sweden

Selcen.ozturkcan@lnu.se

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2248-0802>

Hrithik Jain

University of Birmingham, Business School

hrithikjain42@gmail.com

Abstract

The fast fashion industry has a substantial environmental impact with its increasing worldwide consequences through the supply network (Stahel, 2016). Subsequently, recent years have seen the rise of slow fashion as a more responsible consumption movement (Chi et al., 2021) which is particularly important as Generation Z (Gen Z) prefers sustainable, functional, and pleasing fashion experiences (Youn and Cho, 2021). For instance, the emergence of digital and immersive experiences using technologies such as augmented and virtual reality (AR/VR) and Metaverse has been observed in recent years (Boardman et al., 2020). However, the lack of commitment by responsible brands to innovate with digital and immersive experiences raises questions about the potential trade-offs between sustainability and immersive customer experiences. More specifically, can experiential and immersive technological developments (such as the Metaverse) that improve customer experience offer sustainable revolutionary solutions, even though responsible fashion retail is typically associated with the traditional apparel industry (e.g., classical tailoring, seasonal fashion, and mending)? In other words, can Metaverse help responsible fashion retailers offer revolutionary sustainable solutions?

To explore this topic, we conducted interviews with 16 individuals from Gen Z. According to our results, Gen Z views responsible fashion retail as strongly associated with quality and sustainability but also as "boring" and outdated. That said, interestingly, even though the Metaverse provides quick access to 3D universes and excitement, our study revealed that the participants, despite being aware of the Metaverse, had little to no experience with the brand experiences facilitated. Despite prior unfamiliarity, individuals found these encounters "fun" and educational after being introduced to them for this study. We discovered that the lack of interaction with brands that offer Metaverse experiences is possibly due to a mismatch between Gen Z's purchasing power and those that offer Metaverse experiences (i.e., designer brands). Although Gen Z is digitally literate, enjoys assuming virtual identities, and playing digital games, their purchasing power remains constrained when it comes to actual consumption, and expensive designer goods remain inaccessible to them.

Furthermore, according to our interviewees, Gen Z perceives responsible products and services as lacking in variety, style, and outdated, despite their commitment to responsible brands. However, the customisability of these products and services (tailored to needs) was perceived as a positive brand service. This is interesting, as using digital innovations, such as Metaverse, responsible retailers can reach out to new customers and improve their customisation process more cost-effectively and revolutionise the sustainable fashion concept. The novel retail innovations have the potential to reposition the so-called "boring" image of responsible brands as more engaging and dynamic without compromising on their commitment to sustainability.

Keywords *responsible fashion retail, Metaverse, Generation Z, sustainable revolution*

References

Boardman, R., Henninger, C. E., & Zhu, A. (2020). Augmented reality and virtual reality: new drivers for fashion retail? In *Technology-driven sustainability* (pp. 155-172). Palgrave Macmillan, Cham.

Chi T., Gerard J., Yu Y. & Wang Y., (2021) A study of U.S. consumers' intention to purchase slow fashion apparel: understanding the key determinants, *International Journal of Fashion Design, Technology and Education*, 14:1, 101-112

Stahel, W. R. (2016). The circular economy. *Nature*, 531(7595), 435-438.

Youn, S.Y. and Cho, E., 2021. CSR ads matter to luxury fashion brands: a construal level approach to understand Gen Z consumers' eWOM on social media. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management: An International Journal*